

SOME NEW GENERIC RECORDS TO THE FUNGI OF INDIA

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Abstract:

In the present paper seven fungal taxa belonging to seven different genera of different groups viz. Plasmodiophoromycetous *Tetramyxa* (1 spp.), Pyrenomycetous *Mycocitrus* (1 spp.), Loculoascomycetous *Parmulina* (1 spp.), Hypomycetous *Acroconidiellina* (1 spp.), Chuppia (1 spp.) and Hymenostilbe (1 spp.) and Coelomycetous *Lecanosticta* (1 spp.) have been taxonomically studied and reported as new generic records to the fungi of India. Out of these six genera are parasitic on higher plants and one is on the insect as host. Most of these genera are very rare and limited in their geographical distribution especially – *Tetramyxa*, *Mycocitrus*, *Parmulina*, *Chuppia* and *Lecanosticta* and they are only known by their type species or only 2-5 species. One new species viz. *Chuppia brideliae* Kavale and M. S. Patil (2007) has been proposed and published by the authors on the basis description of the taxon compared with existing monotypic species viz. smaller conidia and the host genus is different.

Keywords: Mycotaxonomy, *Tetramyxa*, *Mycocitrus*, *Parmulina*, *Acroconidiellina*, *Chuppia*, *Hymenostilbe*, *Lecanosticta*, New Generic Records.

Introduction

In continuation of taxonomical studies on fungal flora of Southern Kolhapur district and its neighboring areas, the authors came across several new and interesting fungi collected from different localities become new generic records to the fungi of India. In present investigation the collected and described fungal taxa viz. *Tetramyxa marina* Lapkin and Avidor, *Mycocitrus phyllostachydis* (Syd.) Doi, *Parmulina japonica* Hino and Katumoto, *Acroconidiellina arecae* (Berk. and Br.) M.B.Ellis, *Chuppia brideliae* Kavale and M. S. Patil, and *Lecanosticta gaubae* (Petrak) v. Arx are mostly foliicolous and they are mostly parasitic on the vascular plants except *Hymenostilbe longispora* Samson and Evans which is parasitic on insect host. The genera like *Tetramyxa*, *Mycocitrus*, *Parmulina*, *Chuppia* and *Lecanosticta* are very rare and limited in their geographical distribution and they are only known by their type species or only 2-5 species. On the basis their limited occurrence on specific hosts and up-to-date literature, the fungal taxa have been studied and described by the authors become new generic records to the fungi of India.

Materials and Methods

The fresh living materials were collected repeatedly visits to specific localities of Southern Kolhapur district (Maharashtra State, India) and its neighbouring areas. These materials were critically examined by usual laboratory methods. The collections were identified with the help of up-to-date available literature to their respective genera, species and varieties along with their hosts. New taxon has been proposed and described purely on morphological basis and host specificity. Ranges of variations of the same taxon collected from different seasons were also taken into consideration. The materials have been deposited in Herbarium Cryptogamae Indiae Orientalis (H.C.I.O.), New Delhi, India and their duplicates in Mycological Herbarium, Department of Botany, Shivaji University, Kolhapur (Maharashtra State, India) under W. I. F. (Fungi of Western India) for future reference.

Results and Discussion

Genus: *Tetramyxa* Goebel, Flora 67: 517, 1884.

The genus *Tetramyxa* was established by Goebel in 1884, with the type species *T. parasitica* Goebel. It belonged to the order Plasmodiophorels of the family Plasmodiophoraceae and characterized by resting spores united in small clusters or more or less compact cytosori and resting spores usually arranged in tetrads and dyads. Zoosporangia and zoospores unknown (Karling, 1942 and 1974). It is further characterized the spores often separating and lying singly; plasmodia small, become parietal in host cell at maturity and cleaving into uninucleate spore mother cells which usually divide twice to form tetrads of the resting spores. The genus is known by its 5 species (Lipkin, et al., 1974; <http://www.indexfungorum.org/Names/Names.asp>, 16 Nov., 2025). The genus appears to be comparatively rare in occurrence but widely distributed. It makes new generic record to the fungi of India

Type species: *T. parasitica* Goebel

Tetramyxa marina Lapkin and Avidor, Nova Hedwigia 23 (3-4): 809, 1974.

= *Plasmodiophora halophilae* Ferdinandsen and Winge, Centralbl. Bakt.

Parasitente II, 37: 167, 1913.

= *Sorosporium marina* Kundalkar and Patil, Indian Phytopath, 36 (3): 521, 1983.

Sori foliicolous, confined to the leaf base. Infected parts become swollen and yellowish, innate, 100-260 per leaf base, irregularly crowded, filling the entire cortex, oval to angular due to mutual pressure, young hyaline, at maturity dark-brown and opaque, surrounded by a non-striated thick, hyaline sheath, multispored, 85-300 x 120-325 μm ; spores one-celled, spherical, brown, thick-walled, smooth, grouped in tetrads or diads or free, crowded, 4-5 μm in diameter. Germination not observed.

Habit: In the leaf bases of *Halophila beccaridis* Ascherson (Fam.: Hydrocharitaceae), Ratnagiri (M. S.), 16-6-1978, Dr. Ghewade, K. S., H.C.I.O. – 33756 and W.I.F. 1652.

Remarks: The species of the host genus *Halophila* and its four species out of ten have been infected by two plasmodiophoraceous species of two genera viz. *Plasmodiophora* and *Tetramyxa*. *P. halophilae* Ferdinandsen and Winge reported from Java. and Kenya on *H. deciens* and *H. ovata*, while *T. marina* Lipkin and Avidor has been collected on *H. stipulacea* and *H. ovata* from Red and Mediterrean seas from Israel, especially in the leaf-bases or petioles. The genus is known by five species and the present species strictly confined to the marine species of the genus *Halophila*. *Tetramyxa*, the genus strictly characterized by the spores (cysts) organized into tetrads, of course, may occur in diads or sometimes single. Kundalkar and Patil, M.S. (1983) who proposed a new species of *Sorosporium* viz. *S. marina* a marine species of *Halophila* in the Arabian sea at Ratnagiri (M.S.) collected by Ghewade and studied by Patil and Kundalkar in which sori developed at the bases of the leaves, slightly

hypertrophied and many sori in the leaf mesophyll with spores organized into tetrads and diads, brownish in colour except sori found covered by hyaline sheath, and thus, has made it as synonym of *T. marinia* Lipkin and Avidor. It has been also collected on the species of *Halophila*, strictly marine in habit, sori in the base or petiole of the leaves, and spores brownish in colour and in tetrads and thus, referred to it. *H. beccaridis* Ascherson is an additional host. It is a new record to the Fungi of India.

Genus: *Mycocitrus* Moller, Bot. Mitt. Tropen 9: 297, 1901.

The genus *Mycocitrus* has been established by Moller, A. (1901) with the type species *M. aurantium* Moller. It belongs to the family Hypocreaceae of the order Hypocreales, Pyrenomycetes (Doi, Y., 1967). The genus is characterized by perithecia immersed more or less completely in a compact stroma; stromata superficial or erumpent through substrate; stromata super white, very large, tuberous, arising from a foot-like base; perithecia produced in successive generations forming several layers embedded in the stroma; asci cylindric, unitunicate, long, non-parphysate and 8-spored; ascospores two-celled, elliptical, hyaline, smooth or rough. It produces a conidial state belonged to the form genus *Cephalosporium* Corda an anamorph is any non-sexual manifestation of a fungus (Hennebert & Weresub, 1979) and may serve a multiplicity of roles-like propagation, survival and spermatization (Samules & Blackwell, 2001). Generally synonymized with *Acremonium* (Seifert, K. A. & W. Gams, 2001). The genus is known by 8 species (<http://www.indexfungorum.org/Names/Names.asp>, 16 Nov., 2025). Species are strictly graminicolous. It is a new generic record to the Fungi of India.

Type species: *M. aurantium* A. Moller

Mycocitrus phyllostachydis (Syd.) Doi, Bull. Nat. Sci. Mus. Tokyo, 10 (1): 31-36, 1967;

Basio.: *Ustilaginoides phyllostachydis* Syd., Mem. Herb. Boiss. 4: 5, 1900.

= *Hypocreopsis phyllostachydis* (Syd.) Miyake and Hara, Bot. Mag. Tokyo 24: 333, 1910.

= *Shiraiella phyllostachydis* (Syd.) Hara, Bot. Mag. Tokyo, 28: 402, 1914.

Stromata grayish-white when young, protuberate at the nodal region of the culms, roughened with deeply embedded perithecia which are filled with old ascospores and mycelia, upto 1-1.5 cm in diameter; mycelia more or less radiately arranged but interwoven at random in some part of stromata, 2.3-4 µm thick; Perithecia completely immersed in the stroma, globose or vertically elongated, pseudoparenchymatous wall, covered with an outer layer of yellowish, thick-walled cells, inner cells hyaline, thin-walled, upto 140-180 µm in vertical diameter; asci and ascospores not seen. Conidial state also not observed.

Habit: Parasitic on the culms of *Ischaemum diplopogon* Hook (Fam.: Poaceae), Dapoli, (Dist.-Ratnagiri, M.S.), 14-8-1995 and on the culms of *Dichanthium annulatum* (Forsk.) Stapf (Fam.: Poaceae), Shivaji University Campus, Kolhapur (M. S.), 17-6-2001, M. S. Patil, H.C.I.O. – 45588 and W.I.F. Nos. 1999, 2000 respectively.

Remarks: The genus *Mycocitrus* Moller is known by only three species. The type species *M. aurantium* Moller reported from Brazil (Moller, 1901). This species reported by Yoshimichi Doi (1967) viz. *M. phyllostachydis* (Syd.) Doi. on the branches of *Phyllostachys pubescens* and *P. nigra* from Japan. Present collections morphologically matched well to *M. phyllostachydis* (Syd.) Doi and thus, referred to it. However, the collections differed from each other in respect of size and number of stromata. The stromata on *Dichanthium annulatum* (Forsk.) Stapf, are few in number but larger in size than on *Ischaemum diplopogon* Hooker. This makes a new record to the Fungi of India. *Dichanthium annulatum* (Forsk.) Stapf and *Ischaemum diplopogon* Hook. are the additional new host records.

Genus: *Parmulina* Theiss. and H. Syd., Anns. Mycol; 12: 195, 1914.

The genus *Parmulina* was established by Theissen and Sydow, H. in 1914. It belongs to the family Parmulariaceae of the order Dothideales, Loculoascomycetes (v.Ar.x and Muller, 1975). The genus is characterized by external hyphae absent; ascomata superficial, scutate or disc-like, orbicular, blackish, attached to the leaves of the host plants with the central portion to the surface and connected with intracellular hypostromata; locules linearly, arranged and dehisced at the apex; asci clavate, with short stipes bitunicate and 8-spored; ascospores 1-septate, hyaline to brown. The genus is known by its 9 species (<http://www.indexfungorum.org>). The species of the genus strictly confined to the members of the family Euphorbiaceae. It is a new generic record to the Fungi of India.

Type species: *P. exculpta* (Berk.) Thiess. and Sydow

Parmulina japonica Hino and Katumoto, Journ. Jap. Bot., 36: 378, 1961.

Ascomata amphigenous on leaves, sparse or subgregarious, solitary, sometime confluent, flattened disc-like and orbicular in shape, radial in structure, 2-3 mm in diameter, 55-60 µm in height, fuliginous and attach themselves to leaves of host plant at a short foot of the central portion of under surface, locules 22-30 in number, radially arranged at upper surface of the ascomata, linear to oblong, dichotomously branched at the apex, longitudinally dehiscent and 500-650 µm in length; asci cylindrical to cylindrical-clavate, rounded at the apex, with short stipe, containing eight ascospores in two rows, and 60-90 x 14-18 µm; ascospores oblong fusiform, 1-septate at the middle portion, not or slightly constricted at the septum, hyaline at first, then brownish, smooth, 18.5-23 x 7-10 µm.

Habit: On the leaves of unknown member of the family Euphorbiaceae, Watangi (Tal.-Ajara. Dist.-Kolhapur, M. S.), 2-10-2001, T. R. Kavale, H.C.I.O. - 45589 and W.I.F. - 2003.

Remarks: Hino and Katumoto (1961) have described this species and collected on the leaves of *Daphniphyllum teijsmanni* Zoll. from Sikoku (Japan). The present collection collected on the leaves of Euphorbiaceous member and matched well in all morphological respect except larger diameter of ascomata i.e. up to 3 mm and locules are dichotomously branched at the margin hence, referred to it. It makes new record to the Fungi of India.

Genus: *Acroconidiellina* M.B. Ellis, Mycol. Pap., 125: 22-27, 1971.

The genus *Acroconidiellina* was established by M. B. Ellis in 1971. It belongs to the family Dematiaceae of the order Hyphomycetales. The genus is characterized by mycelium superficial composed of a network of branched and anastomosing, septate, subhyaline, brown, dark-brown or olivaceous-brown, smooth hyphae; sclerotia often formed, more or less spherical, frequently dorsiventrally compressed, smooth, tuberculate or setose, dark blackish-brown to black; setae often formed either on hyphae or on sclerotia, straight or flexuous, subulate, multiseptate, brown or dark-brown, smooth, rugulose or verruculose; hyphopodia absent; conidiophores macronematous, mononematous, mostly simple, rarely branched, straight or flexuous, pale-brown, smooth, rugulose or verruculose, multiseptate; conidiogenous cells polytretic, integrated, terminal or intercalary, sympodial, cicatrized; conidia solitary, acropleurogenous, ellipsoidal, obturbinate or obclavate, subhyaline to brown or dark-brown, echinulate or verruculose, 1-5 septate or pseudoseptate. The genus is known by its 4 species (<http://www.indexfungorum.org/Names/Names.asp>, 16 Nov., 2025). In India, the genus is unknown. So, it is a new generic record to the fungi of India.

Type species: *A. loudetiae* M.B.Ellis

Acroconidiellina arecae (Berk. and Br.) M.B.Ellis, Mycol. Pap., 125: 20-27, 1971.

Basio.: *Helminthosporium arecae* Berk. and Br., F. of Ceyl. n. 883, 1873.

= *Brachysporium arecae* (Berk. and Br.) Sacc., Syll. Fungorum 4: 429, 1886.

Colonies hypophyllous, small, orbicular, often punctiform, numerous and close together, dark blackish-brown, hairy; mycelium superficial and composed of a close network of branched and anastomosing, smooth, mid to dark-brown, 4-7 μm thick hyphae, but each colony is anchored to the substratum by a narrow hypha which grows down through a stoma. The hyphae bears numbers of conidiophores and some times also setae; conidiophores erect or suberect, straight or slightly flexuous, unbranched mid to dark-brown, rugulose or verruculose, thick-walled septate up to 175-216 μm long, but usually shorter, 5-6 μm thick at the base, 9-10 μm at the apex; setae erect, straight or flexuous, cylindrical to subulate, mid to dark-brown, rugulose or verruculose, thick-walled, septate up to 516-605 μm long, 6-9 μm thick; conidia straight, obturbinate to obclavate, usually 3-4 septate, with central cells verrucose, mid-dark brown, cells at each end paler and smoother, 52-63 μm long, 18-19 μm thick in the broadest part.

Habit: On the living leaves of *Areca catechu* Linn. (Fam.: Arecaceae), Gangabag (Tal.-Ajara, Dist.-Kolhapur, M.S.), 10-10-1999, T.R.Kavale, H.C.I.O.- 46904, W.I.F. - 2015.

Remarks: The genus *Acroconidiellina* is known by 4 valid species (M.B.Ellis, 1971, 1976) and reported on *Loudetia arundinaceae* from Tanzania; *Chloris* spp. from Argentina, U.S.A. and Zambia; on *Trichachne insularis* from Cuba and on *Areca catechu* from Sri Lanka, Malaya, New Guinea, Phillippines, Singapore etc. However, the present collection well matched with the *A. arecae* (Berk and Br.) M.B. Ellis except smaller conidiophores, and thus, referred to it. It makes new record to the Fungi of India.

Genus: *Chuppia* Deighton, Mycol. Pap., 101: 32, 1965.

The genus *Chuppia* has been established by Deighton in 1965, with the type species *C. sarcinifera* Deighton. This genus belonged to the family Dematiaceae of the order Hyphomycetales. It is characterized by colonies orbicular or effuse, dark blackish-brown; mycelium superficial, densely aggregated and closely entangled and coiled around the upper part of the leaf hairs; stroma none; setae and hyphopodia absent; conidiophores micronematous, flexuous, irregularly branched, golden brown to dark olivaceous-brown, smooth; conidiogenous cells monoblastic integrated, intercalary, determinate, cylindrical or doliiform, denticulate, denticles very broad and conical, conidia solitary, pleurogenous, simple, ellipsoidal, subspherical or irregular in shape, dark golden-brown, muriform and strongly constricted at the septa (sarciniform), smooth to verruculose, with protuberant hilum. The genus is monotypic known by its type species and reported from Venezuela (South America, 1965). It is a new generic record to the fungi of India.

Type species: *C. sarcinifera* Deighton

Chuppia brideliae Kavale and M. S. Patil, *J. Mycol. Pl. Pathol*, 37 (1): 72-73, 2007

Colonies hypophyllous, orbicular or effuse and spreading, dark blackish-brown; mycelium superficial, densely aggregated, septate and closely coiled; stroma none; setae and hyphopodia absent; conidiophores micronematous, flexuous, irregularly branched, golden brown to dark olive-brown, smooth, conidiogenous cells monoblastic integrated, cylindrical to doliiform, up to 7 μm in long and 5 μm in broad; conidia solitary, pleurogenous, simple, ellipsoidal, subspherical or irregular in shape, dark-brown, muriform and constricted at the septa (sarciniform), smooth or verruculose with protuberant hilum, up to 13-14 x 7-10 μm .

Habit: On the living leaves of *Bridelia retusa* Spreng. (Fam.: Euphorbiaceae), Gavase (Tal.-Ajara Dist.-Kolhapur, M. S.), 13-2-2003, T. R. Kavale, H.C.I.O. - 45565 (a type), W.I.F. - 1983.

Remarks: Deighton (1965) raised the new genus viz. *Chuppia* based on the collection collected from Venezuela (South America) on the leaves of *Solanum* species as *C. sarcinifera* Deighton, a monotypic genus. There is one more

genus viz. *Pseudochuppia* is known from India viz. *P.sarcinispota* sp. nov. collected on the leaves of *Grewia* species (Fam.: Tiliaceae) from North India by Kamal, et al. (1984). Both the genera appears to be similar by the overall morphology but differ from each other by the conidiophores and the conidiogenous cells. As to compare our present material, origin of the conidia are different as well as conidiophores also differ morphologically. Thus, our material belongs to the genus *Chuppia* Deighton. However, the conidia in the present material are comparatively very small in size as well as the host genus different. Therefore, on the basis of these characters, a new species *C. brideliae* sp. nov. has been proposed. It makes new record to the fungi of India.

Genus: *Hymenostilbe* (Ditm.) Petch, Trans. Brit. Myc. Soc. 21: 55: 1949.

The genus *Hymenostilbe* was established by Petch with *H. sphecophila* as the type species and characterized by synnemata which are many and developed from the dead body of the insect, separate, stalked, simple, brown, cylindrical, terminating into a globose head; conidiophores bearing conidia terminally and singly; conidia one-celled, oval or spherical, hyaline, smooth-walled and minute. Perfect state belonged to the genus *Cordyceps* (Tanda and Nagase, 1978). The genus is known by it's 29 species (<http://www.indexfungorum.org/Names/Names.asp>, 16 Nov., 2025), however 11 species are doubtful (Hywel-Jones, 1995; Samson and Evas, 1975). It makes new generic record to the Fungi of India.

Type species: *H. sphecophila* (Ditm.) Petch

Hymenostilbe longispora Samson and Evans, Mycol. Research, 100 (5): 613-619, 1996.

Synnemata many and developed from the dead body of the ant (black), mostly from the joints, separate, stalked, simple, cylindrical, terminating into globose head which is dark brown, 1-2 mm long and head 200-300 µm in diameter, composed of compactly arranged basally branched but simple conidiophores bearing conidia terminally and singly; conidia one-celled, oval or spherical, thin-walled, hyaline and 1-2 x 2-4 µm and smooth, black. Perfect state belonged to *Cordyceps sphecophila* (Kl.) Saccardo reported from Formosa (Tanda and Nagase, 1978), infecting to wasps and bees (Thailand).

Habit: Collected on dead black ant viz. *Camponotus compressus* Worker (Fam.: Formicidae) on the leaf of grass, Shivaji University Campus, Kolhapur (M.S.), Sept. 1978, Dr. M. S. Patil, W.I.F. – 1024.

Remarks: Mahamulkar, S.H. (2001) has described a synnematous fungus viz. *Hymenostilbe sphecophila* (Ditm.) Petch, collected on dead black ant (*Camponotus compressus* Worker) in his thesis. However, Hywel-Jones (1995) described *Hymenostilbe* and *Cordyceps* species infecting to wasps and bees from Thailand. The species *Hymenostilbe longispora* Samson and Evans having black synnemata, longer conidiogenous cells and smaller conidia. Thus, the present collection matched to *H. longispora* Samson and Evans except the conidia, which are smaller. No perfect state was found associated with the dead insect. It makes new record to the Fungi of India.

Genus: *Lecanosticta* H. Syd. apud P. Syd. and Pet., Anns Mycol. 20: 211, 1922.

= *Phrgmogloeum* Petrak, Sydowia, 8: 158, 1954.

The genus *Lecanosticta* was established by Sydow in 1922 with the type species *L. acicola* (Thum.) Sydow. It is an anamorphic state of the genus *Mycosphaerella* and belongs to class Coelomycetes of the order Melanconiales. The genus is characterized by parasitic on leaves; conidiomata usually acervular-cupulate, immersed in the host tissue, with a wide, apical opening; conidiogenous cells holoblastic, conidiogenesis solitary, entero-percurrent or sympodial, annellidic, 1-2 annellations; conidia 2-4 euseptate, cylindrical clavate, pale brown, often punctulate, forming cirrhi or slimy masses. The genus is known by it's 2 species (v. Arx, 1983). It is a new generic record to the Fungi of India.

Type species: *L. acicola* (Thum.) Sydow

Lecanosticta gaubae (Petraek) v. Arx and O. Const., Mycology Proc., 86 (1): 31-35, 1983.

Basio.: *Phragmogloeum gaubae* Petraek, Sysowia, 8: 158, 1954.

Parasitic on leaves, epiphyllous, pale-brown coloured slimy or sticky mass of conidia on upper surface of leaves; conidiomata acervular-cupulate, immersed in the host tissue, with a wide apical opening, upto 118-160 x 107-118 µm; conidiogenous cells lining the inner basal wall, short, cylindrical, amuliform or conical, conidiogenesis is solitary, entero-percurrent or sympodial; conidia pigmented cylindrical, clavate, pale-brown, slightly verrucose, 2-4 septate, often punctulate, forming cirrhi or slimy masses, upto 37-55 x 4-6 µm. Perfect state not observed.

Habit: On the living leaves of *Eucalyptus globulus* Labill. (Fam.: Myrtaceae), Atyal (Tal.-Gadhinglaj, Dist.-Kolhapur, M.S.), 3-1-2005, T. R. Kavale, H.C.I.O.- 46901 and W.I.F.-2054.

Remarks: This species has been reported by v. Arx and O. Constantinescu (1983) from Australia on the member of the family Myrtaceae viz. *Callistemon sieberi*. The present collection collected on *Eucalyptus globulus* Labill. also belonging to the same family, found to be quite identical in respect of morphology and dimension of the conidia and thus, referred to it. It makes new record to the Fungi of India and *Eucalyptus globulus* Labill. is an additional host

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